

D9.1 Data Management Plan

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Management Plan
template

Executive summary

This DMP is a general plan that applies to all research sub-projects in the MIDA project.

It is an elaboration of information stated in MIDA's Scientific Proposal, the paragraph on Open Access to Research Data in GRANT Agreement 813547 and the Consortium Agreement for MIDA. For all sub-projects, the Early Stage Researchers and their supervisors will write an individual DMP as a result of a data management training during the first MIDA training event on 1st November 2019 in Utrecht.

These data management plans will follow the general MIDA guidelines stated in this document. They will additionally contain details of the type of data collected or generated and how these are made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-Useable).

Research data generated in the course of the MIDA project that is not restricted by law (GDPR, IPR) will be made available to the wider scientific community by publication in a data archive such as Zenodo at the end of the project.

Personal information about human individuals will be dealt with according to European and national legislation as specified in the MIDA Scientific proposal (see paragraph 5.2 of the Grant Agreement).

Further ethical issues related to research data will be dealt with in Work Package 10. In order to guarantee long-term access, research data will be stored as much as possible in sustainable formats and documented according to discipline specific standards and licenses.

1. Prepare

1.1 Data Collection

Within the MIDA project, a number of 15 Early Stage Researchers will collect and generate a variety of research data in order to answer the research questions raised in their individual projects.

They will collect existing data such as audiovisual materials, social media data, videoclips, websites, digital collections, biographical database, (digital copies of) printed materials, manuscripts, drawings and photographs, reviews and news articles.

Furthermore, they will create interview data, survey data and video & audio-recordings. As the MIDA project deals partly with unsustainable and changing data sources from social media and the internet, dedicated training and internships will focus on how to secure access to these sources for research purposes.

At the end of the project, research data suitable for re-use will be archived in sustainable and interoperable data formats.

1.2 Data Documentation

When data is collected and stored in the course of the project, it will be documented according to community driven standards, if available.

Conventions on filenames, folder structures and information in readme files can help to guarantee understanding of the datasets on the long term.

For data archived at the end of the project, metadata will be added according to the standard used by the data repository (e.g. Dublin Core metadata).

All other documentation needed to understand and re-use the datasets will be stored together with the data.

2. Handling research Data-management

2.1 Data Storage and Back-up

To store and share data securely during the project, the researchers will use My Core Space, provided by the CNRS, as well as secure facilities provided by their host institutions (Beneficiaries).

My Core Space complies with the information security policy of CNRS and back-ups are made on a regular basis.

The researchers will ensure that back-up procedures are in place. If not, they will make regular back-up themselves.

They will comply with local information security policies and, if available, will ask for support from local support staff, privacy officers and the institutional Data Protection Officer.

2.2 Data Access and Security

Many of the data collected within the sub-projects contain personal or sensitive information.

As stated in the paragraph on Personal Data in MIDA's Scientific Proposal, personal data will be replaced with code names as soon as possible.

Keys to re-identify the data will be kept in a separate, secure storage space. Data will be anonymised whenever possible in relation to the research questions.

Participants will be asked for consent to share datasets within the network and access to these datasets will be organised accordingly. For this purpose, the CNRS provides My-Core, that enables encryption.

Consent forms will mention the option of eventual secondary use. If consent is not obtained for secondary use, data that can be traced back to individual persons will be destroyed after completion of the proposal.

Privacy officers at the host institutions will provide advice on local procedures in place for handling and processing personal data, in accordance with national and European law.

3. Preserve and Share

3.1 Data preservation and Archiving

Copyright protected materials and raw data that contain personal or sensitive data can not be shared with the wider community.

These are kept for the purpose and the duration of the research project only.

Processed and anonymised datasets and all other datasets that can not be traced back to individual persons will be archived according to the FAIR guidelines, meaning that community standards are adopted as well as licences that permit re-use.

The individual data management plans will provide more detail on how the FAIR principles will be applied to the subprojects.

3.2 Data Sharing and Reuse

Research data resulting from the MIDA project that can be of interest for the scientific community or the general public will be made available for re-use via a repository such as **Zenodo** with a license that allows re-use and a reference to the ERC grant number.

The data repository will provide a persistent identifier to link to and cite the datasets in publications.

With the data, all documentation and, if applicable, software will be provided with the data in order to enable re-use.

Annex

ESR's Data Management Plan template*

The Research Data Management Regulations Leiden University requires researchers to write a data management plan at the start of a research project. Contact the Centre for Digital Scholarship at the University Libraries Leiden if you need help: cds@library.leidenuniv.nl. Please check for the latest version of this template at the website of the CDS.

* This template is based on the 3TU data management plan, the University of Bath data management plan and the Data Management Checklist of the University of Western Sydney.

ESR's Name and contact details	Please include email address and telephone number
Name of project and group	Name your supervisors
Description of your research	Briefly describe your research to help others understand the purposes for which the data are being collected or created. <i>Max. 50 words.</i>
Project duration	Start: DD-MM-YYYY End: DD-MM-YYYY
Names of people and their responsibilities for data management	Responsibilities can be collecting, storing, documenting, sharing and archiving the data. <i>Naming anyone with specific roles and responsibilities for data management is especially important for collaborative projects that involve many researchers and/or partner organisations.</i>
Funding body(ies)	European Commission – Research Executive Agency
Grant number	H2020-MSCA-ITN MIDA 813547
Partner organisations	If applicable. These may be research partners that use your data, or that you use data from.
Ethical review	If applicable mention the registration number of your protocol and the name of the Ethical Committee.
Processing of Personal Data	If you process personal data, you are legally required to fill out a Data Processing Inventory. Personal data refers to any information that can be traced back to a person. This information could be a name, address or location, but it could also be bank account numbers, telephone numbers or post codes with house numbers. <input type="radio"/> I do not collect personal data. <input type="radio"/> I collect personal data and I will answer questions P1 and P2. <i>For more information, see: https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/ict/privacy-and-data-protection/personal-data/personal-data/service-units?cf=service-units</i>
Part 1 – Research Data Processing Inventory	You can contact the information manager of your faculty or the Data Protection Officer for the latest template of the Data Processing Inventory. <input type="radio"/> I did fill out the Data Processing Inventory and will attach it to this DMP <input type="radio"/> I did not yet fill out the Data Processing Inventory <input type="radio"/> Not applicable, I do not collect personal data <i>See also: https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/ict/privacy-and-data-protection/general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/service-units?cf=service-units</i>
Part 2 – Description of Risks and Corrective Measures	After completing Part 1, you should complete the Description of Risks and Corrective Measures (part 2). <input type="radio"/> I did perform a Description of Risks and Corrective Measures and will attach it to this DMP <input type="radio"/> I have not yet filled out the Description of Risks and Corrective Measures. <input type="radio"/> Not applicable, I do not collect personal data. <i>You can find the latest version at: https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/ict/privacy-and-data-protection/general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/data-processing-register/service-units?cf=service-units</i>

Annex

About this Data Management Plan

Date written DD-MM-YYYY

Date last update DD-MM-YYYY

Version A new version of the DMP should be created whenever important changes to the project occur due to inclusion of new data sets, changes in consortium policies or external factors.
Don't forget to include the date.

Changes in this version of the Data Management Plan

Component	Progress / Execution
	Please describe briefly what progress you have made, any questions or issues you have encountered and want to discuss, etc.
1. Data collection	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
2. Data storage and back-up	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
3. Data documentation	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
4. Data access, sharing and reuse	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
5. Data preservation and archiving	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>